

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Tifuntoh**FIRST NAME:** Christopher Konde**PROGRAM CODE:** MME**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** DR. GULMA**Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 3%

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List 5 to 7 key concepts with page numbers in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Best Practices for Writing a Quality Academic Essay (EUCLID 2024, 7-12)
2. Punctuation (EUCLID 2024, 16-23)
3. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2024, 34-39)
4. American Vs. British English (EUCLID 2024, 25-32)
5. General Style Guide (EUCLID 2024, 41-42)

BEST PRACTICES FOR WRITING QUALITY ACADEMIC ESSAYS

1) INTRODUCTION

When I finished my master's degree in Monitoring and Evaluation (MME), I sought ways to take my knowledge of Monitoring and Evaluation to a new level. I was unsure where to engage this new journey, I reached out to some colleagues and one recommended the EUCLID to me. When I looked into the requirements for admission to the Doctor of Philosophy, I realized that I could quickly get these documents ready on time. I submitted all the required documents and was delighted when I was offered the measurement, monitoring, and evaluation opportunity.

I quickly read through the EUCLID protocol to understand all my obligations as a student. I registered on the LMS portal. I watch all the tutorial videos more than once. I read the revised ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma. This enabled me to understand the best practices for writing quality academic essays.

In this response paper, I will discuss the best practices for writing quality academic essays. This will cover the best practices for writing a quality academic essay, punctuation, plagiarism, American Vs. British English, the general style guide, and some rules of thumb for writing academic papers.

2) BEST PRACTICES FOR WRITING A QUALITY ACADEMIC ESSAY

This chapter of the ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack for period one explores the basics of easy writing. It indicates some best practices for writing a quality essay. It expands on engaging the writing of a paper. It highlighted that they should commit time to the task when planning to write an academic paper. I realized that to produce quality work, I need to start early and develop a plan for the write-up before starting. I also realized that it is very important to properly research the topic. After understanding the topic, the next important thing is reading and researching what to write (EUCLID 2024, 8).

After organizing the research idea, it is important to write a first draft according to the framework of the essay (EUCLID 2024, 10). In this section, I learned that the structure of the essay should consist of an introduction, a body, and a conclusion. This chapter also dives into the referencing of the essay. Here, the author's emphasizes on guiding against plagiarism, indicate how the institution would want the writers to reference materials, and insist on consistency throughout the essay. This section ended with a clear emphasis on proper editing. Essays dramatically improve upon careful editing (EUCLID 2024, 11).

Reading through the ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack for period one, I realized that in writing academic essays, I have to be very clear and precise about the language used, the English language version. I am convinced that reading this chapter has given me additional insight into the key best practices for writing quality academic essays.

3) PUNCTUATION

In this chapter, I learned the main punctuation marks their uses, and the differences between punctuation marks. I understood that proper essay writing cannot be well done without correct us of the appropriate punctuation marks. In this section, I learned how to correctly use apostrophes, brackets, bullet points commas, colons, and semicolons. This section also enabled me to understand how to employ hyphens, dashes, ellipses, full stops, exclamation, questions, and quotation marks.

When writing academic essays, I now know how to correctly use the apostrophe S ('s) for words that end with S and those that do not end with an S. This section also helped me know how to correctly contract two words. I learned that brackets are used in place of a pair of dashes or commas around a non-defining phrase (EUCLID 2024, 17).

I also learned not to punctuate the end of bullets in academic essays. Before reading this section, I often had conflicting thoughts on when and how to properly use colons and semicolons. EUCLID (2024, 18) states that colons are used “to introduce a subclause that follows logically from the text before it.”

This section indicated that I should use single quotation marks for direct speech and double quotation marks for direct speech. I also retained that I should not use quotation marks when the quote is displayed. This section also taught me that I should use punctuation marks inside the quote, not outside, for example, according to EUCLID (2024, 23).

If the quotation would have required punctuation in the original form, place the punctuation inside the quotation marks.

Punctuations are very important in writing an academic essay, therefore, I have to often read this section when I am writing any academic essay to be sure that I am respecting all the required situations. Before I start writing, I have to check if the journal has its required punctuation specifications and respect them accordingly.

4) PLAGIARISM

According to EUCLID (2024, 34), plagiarism is “when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information.” Avoiding plagiarism in academic essays is not only the right thing but an ethical one. In academic writing, it is important to give credit to credit to authors whose work is cited in my write-up. To avoid plagiarism, this section highlighted in-text citations, what is quoted, tips about quotations, and paraphrasing.

Here, I learned that in-text citations are when one cites the text being researched within the body of the essay. I also realized that quotations are the exact words of an author (EUCLID 2024, 35). When quoting a long text (over 4 lines), it should be quoted as a paragraph. I also learned that I should limit the use of quotations by using it when there is a very important language that I want to use the quote to highlight from a recognized authority in the field of the researched issue.

In this section, I learned the four key best practices for using paraphrases. When the writer researches a topic and summarizes the ideas of the author, it is termed paraphrasing. I understand here that paraphrases should be my words, in a different style from that of the author, and provide accurate information on the issue. In all, I must still cite the author of the original idea.

It is good that EUCLID introduced plagiarism earlier in the process to prepare students to best avoid this through their academic writing. In this chapter, I have understood plagiarism, how to avoid it, and how to cite paraphrases and footnotes in MS Word.

5) AMERICAN VS BRITISH ENGLISH

I largely studied in a bilingual country where French and English languages are largely used. This is complicated by local vernaculars that have strongly influenced my writing. I have worked with various languages and varied donors, each indicating what language should be used. This situation has enabled me to have this reflection to check out the language required by different stakeholders. Given that I currently work for an American company, my computer is set to American English by default.

Though I had this basic knowledge of the use of different languages, there were lots of things I did not know, and this section of this course has clarified them for me. I have learned the various syntax and punctuations within the different languages, how to look out for the differences, and how to effectively use them in academic writing.

According to EUCLID (2024, 25), “American and British English are both variants of World English. As such, they are more similar than different, especially with "educated" or "scientific" English.” However, through the course, I understood that EUCLID suggests that American English would be used in our entire studies.

6) GENERAL STYLE GUIDE

According to EUCLID (2024, 41), a style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that must be consistent. From this section, I learned that a style guide is important for academic writing as it defines the pattern to document ideas in a coherent and accepted pattern.

A style guide defines the writing roles to be adopted in the essay. The single source indicates the type of English to be adopted in the writing. I have learned that the Chicago Rules (Turabian) is EUCLID’s recommended writing style. I have learned that styles indicate the preferred length of sentences, text layouts, accepted spelling, abbreviations, voice preferences, and headings, among others. I have learned here to use short sentences and an active voice as much as possible.

This chapter has taught me how to consider the accepted style in my papers and essays effectively. I have generally understood styles in academic writing, the importance of adopting a particular style, and what to look for in a style guide. This section has given me additional clarity on why I should often stick to the EUCLID formats.

7) CONCLUSION

This initial period has given me much clarity on engaging writings in the academic milieu in general and EUCLID in particular. This period has given me the perfect introduction I need to size up the seriousness of my work on the PhD course. The materials

(text and videos) have demonstrated that no aspect of academic writing is to be taken lightly.

Through this period, I have retained the best practices in essay writing and revised and updated my understanding of punctuation. I have fully imbibed the process of setting up languages in EUCLID writings, how to avoid plagiarism, and adopting the right writing style, among others. I think I am now ready to start period two of the course.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth Edition. Washington DC: Euclid University Press.

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